

Sustainable Computing in Schools

The issue

Children use more and more digital technology: the Scottish Government has committed to every pupil having a personal digital device in school by the end of 2026.⁶ But children aren't being taught about the sustainability of their devices and technology use, even in schools where sustainability is a priority.

Technology can be used to make positive changes on the climate. However, our technology use is simultaneously damaging the environment - and this is only increasing with the widespread use of AI.

Education and skills for young people are essential in our transition towards a circular economy. There will be 18 million new jobs in the circular economy by 2040, and we need a workforce ready for these jobs of the future.⁷

Why now?

Given the ongoing work on the [Curriculum Improvement Cycle](#) and the development of the new [Circular Economy Strategy](#), we have the opportunity to design elements of the curriculum that meet the need for students to learn about the environmental implications of the technologies they use every day. This will also meet the aims of the [Learning for Sustainability Action Plan 2023-2030](#).

Teachers told us that technology proliferates in schools, but they don't include the environmental impacts of technology in their teaching, such as the resource implications and what we do with e-waste. Teachers saw the importance of students learning about this but lacked resources. By incorporating the environmental impacts of technologies into the curriculum we can prompt more critical thinking about technology use, which is essential as we transition towards a circular economy.

Key facts

In the UK, the average person generates 24kg of e-waste every year - that's the second highest in the world.¹

A typical data centre uses between 11 million and 19 million litres of water per day, roughly the same as a town of 30,000 to 50,000 people.² There are 11 data centres in Scotland alone.³

By 2030, it's predicted the world will throw away nearly 75 million tonnes of e-waste. Only 17% of e-waste is recycled.⁴

£50 million worth of gold will potentially be wasted in Scotland in five years through disposal of electronics devices, including computers and phones.⁵

Recommendations

- The Curriculum Improvement Cycle should incorporate the sustainability of technology, including energy, water and resource use
- The Circular Economy Strategy should make specific reference to learning about the environmental impacts of technology use (this would fit in the Education and Skills section)
- We need new content for teacher training – teachers told us that they don't feel they have the knowledge or experience to teach the sustainability of technology
- We need new example lesson plans for teachers on these topics, we have started this with our resource Sustainable computing in schools

Priority areas

We identified the following focus areas for teaching on the sustainability of computing and technology use:

- Life cycles of computing technologies
- Energy impact of computing technologies
- Using computing to understand and take action on the environment and the climate

About the project

This policy briefing is informed by a research project between the Institute for Design Informatics, University of Edinburgh and Ostrero, funded by the ESRC Digital Good Network through the University of Sheffield (grant reference ES/X502352/1). The project investigates whether sustainability is currently taught as part of computing and technology in Scottish schools and maps potential curricular links between sustainability and computing.

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What teachers told us

“Tech is seen as a magic wand ... Your digital technology will solve everything and nobody thinks about what it takes to produce and to maintain it, and what happens at the end of its life.”

“I have never once been aware of a conversation about how these devices are made, how they are recycled, what happens to them at the end of their life, or the power and the mineral resources that it takes to make all of this.”

“We need statistics, data and information on things like digital footprints and legacy devices. I think it's something that teachers would be really interested in learning more about.”⁸

¹ Friends of the Earth Scotland 'Press release: Electrical waste piled outside Scottish Parliament ahead of vote on new environmental law' June 2024

² BBC News 'Concern UK's AI ambitions could lead to water shortages', February 2025

³ Directorate for Digital: Digital Connectivity Division, 'Green datacentres programme update', June 2024

⁴ Friends of the Earth Scotland 'Press release: Electrical waste piled outside Scottish Parliament ahead of vote on new environmental law' June 2024

⁵ Scottish Enterprise, *Digital Technology, Digital Participation and the Circular Economy*, January 2016

⁶ SNP 'A laptop or tablet for every school child: John Swinney's pledge', March 2021

⁷ Sitra 'How does the Circular Economy Change Jobs in Europe?' March 2021 P25

⁸ Quotes from interviews with teachers in Primary and Secondary schools in Scotland, October 2024